

ADABIYOTSHUNOSLIKDA “AYOLLAR ADABIYOTI”NING SHAKLLANISH TARIXI VA RIVOJLANISHI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada adabiyotshunoslikda “Ayollar adabiyoti” ning shakllanish tarixi va o'zbek adabiyotida tutgan o'rni haqida fikr yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: “Ayollar adabiyoti”, tipologik o'xshashliklar, genetik xususiyatlar, mushaira, adabiy maktab.

THE HISTORY AND DEVELOPMENT OF "WOMEN'S LITERATURE" IN LITERARY STUDIES

Abstract. This article discusses the history of the formation of "Women's Literature" in literary studies and its role in Uzbek literature

Key words: "Women's literature", typological similarities, genetic characteristics, poem debate, literary school.

ИСТОРИЯ И РАЗВИТИЕ «ЖЕНСКОЙ ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ» В ЛИТЕРАТУРОВЕДЕНИИ

Аннотация. Ой статье рассматривается история становления «женской литературы» в литературоведении и ее роль в узбекской литературе.

Ключевые слова: «Женская литература», типологическое сходство, генетическая характеристика, литературная школа.

Jahon adabiyotshunosligida ilk bor amerikalik tadqiqotchilar fanga “Ayollar adabiyoti” degan tushunchani olib kirishdi. Zero, XX asr o'rtalariga kelib jahon feminizasiyasi¹ o'z ta'sirini so'z san'ati bo'lmish adabiyotga ham o'tkazayotgan edi. N.Beym 1978 yilda “Ayollar adabiyoti” nomli kitobini nashr qildi. N.Beym ayollar asarlarining o'ziga xos tipologik xususiyatlarini kashf etdi². Unda XIX asrning o'rtalarida katta mashhurlikka ega bo'lgan, biroq keyinchalik ismlari aktualigini yo'qotgan ayol ijodkorlarning asarlari tahlil qilingan. Bular Ketrin - Mariya Sedjvik, Sara Xeyl, A.Dj. Greyvs, Mariya Makintosh, Emma Sautuort va Karolina Li Xens, Mari Kamins va Mariam Kouls Xarris. Yuqoridagi ijodkorlarning asarlarini tahlil qilish borasida Nina Beym “ayollar romani”ning o'ziga xos tipologik xususiyatlarini kashf etdi.

Adabiyotshunoslikda “Ayollar adabiyoti” borasidagi kuzatishlar “Ayollar adabiyotshunosligi” terminologik tushunchasini yuzaga keltirdi. Bu fan hali taraqqiyot davrini o'z boshidan kechirmoqda. “Ayollar adabiyotshunosligi”ga munosib hissa qo'shgan ingliz adibasi Virdjiniya Vulf³ sanaladi. Yapon adabiyotshunoslari “Yaponiya ayollar adabiyoti”ni

¹ феминизм – лотинчада социал ва ижтимоий фаолиятда аёллар ҳуқуқи учун ҳаракат

²Baym N. Woman's fiction: A guide to novels by and about women in America, 1820-1870. – Nhaga; London: Cernel unif.Press. 1978. – 320 p.; Бу ҳақда қаранг: Умурова Г. Зулфия бадийи олами ва поэтик мактаби. Филол. фан. д-ри (DSc)... дисс. – Самарқанд: 2019.

³ Rigney B.H. A wreath upon the grave? The influence of Virginia Woolf on feminist critical theory// Criticism and critical theory.- L.: Arnold, 1984. Б.73

shakllantirgan adibalar ijodini o'rganib, uning o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini, ayol ijodkorlarning qahramon obrazini yaratishdagi genderlik alomatlarini aniqladi. Yu.Rumak mashhur yozuvchilar asarlarini tahlil qilib, ularda genetik jihatdan farqni ko'rsatdi. Chunonchi, yapon adibalari asarlarini yaponcha yozuv (idyografik sillabik, ya'ni aralash yozuv) bilan, erkak yozuvchilar esa xitoycha yozuvda yozgan. Chunki o'rta asrlarda Yaponiyada xitoy tili ilm-fan tili, rasmiy hujjat va olimlar tili deb hisoblangan.

Murakkabligi bois xitoy tilini yapon ayollari o'rgana olmaganlar.⁴ Xuddi shunday o'zbek adabiyotida poetik maktab yaratgan ayol ijodkorlar ham mavjudki, ularning adabiy merosini, estetik olamini tadqiq etish bizlarni mana shu kabi fikrlarga olib keladi. O'zbek adabiyotida ham ayollar adabiyotini keng tadqiq etish uchun yetarlicha manbaa mavjud. Chunki, o'zbek mumtoz adabiyotida ayol ijodkorlarning o'rni va o'z nufuzi bo'lgan. Saroylarda shoiralarning, ijodkor ayollarning maxsus mushoiralari, adabiy anjumanlari muntazam bo'lib o'tgan. Ularning asarlari e'tiroflarga, tahsinlarga sazovor bo'lgan. Jumladan, shoira Nodira, Jahon Otin Uvaysiy, Dilshodi Barno, Anbar Otin kabi ijodkor ayollarning ijodiy merosi o'zbek adabiyotida ayollar adabiyotining ancha ilgari paydo bo'lganiga ishoradir.

Chunki bu shoiralardan katta adabiy maktab qolganki, uning an'analari bugungi kunda ham tadqiq etilmoqda. Ular yaratgan adabiy maktablarda yuzlab yosh shoiralalar shakllangan, ayollarning ilmi, ziyoli, diniy va dunyoviy bilimlarni mukammal egallashi ijodining pafosiga aylangan. Tarixiy yodnomalarda, tazkiralarda ularning adabiyot nazariyasining bilimdoni ekanligi, adabiyotning bir qancha janrlarida ijod qilganligi e'tirof etilgan. Ijodiy jarayonda ayollar obrazi tasviri bilan ayollar adabiyotining o'ziga xos farqli jihatlari mavjud. O'zbek adabiyotining eng sara asarlari ayollarga bag'ishlangan, ularni madh etgan asarlardir. Shuning bilan birga o'zbek shoiralari va adibalari, ularning ijodi, adabiy merosi, mahorati ham o'ziga xosdir. O'zbek adabiyotida maktab yaratgan shoiralaramiz tomonidan yaratilgan adabiy maktablarning – ayollar adabiyotining shakllanishida o'rni beqiyos.

XX asr o'zbek adabiyotida mana shunday adabiy maktab yaratgan shoiralalar sirasiga shoira Zulfiya adabiy maktabini kiritishimiz mumkin. Chunki shoira Zulfiya adabiy maktabi T.Sodiqova, H.Xudoyberdiyeva, O.Hojiyeva, G.Jo'rayeva, H.Ahmedova singari bir qancha iste'dodli shoiralarni yetishtirib berdi. Shubhasiz, adabiy maktab, ijodiy muhitni iste'dodlar yaratadi. Ayni paytda bu muhit yetishib chiqayotgan ijodkorlarning saviyasini belgilaydi. Har bir adabiy maktabning o'rni uning ijodkorlarining iste'dodi orqali baholanishi mumkin. Ayol ijodkorlarning ijodida ayol obrazi, ayol qalbi tasviri o'zgacha tasvirlanadi. Ayol ijodkorlar ayol kishining ruhiyatini erkak ijodkorlardan ko'ra chuqurroq idrok etadi.

Shoira Zulfiya estetikasida alohida ajralib turadigan muhim jihatlar o'zbek ayolining mardonavorligi, ulug' g'oyalarni tarannum qila olish qobiliyati, ajdodlarga xos zukkolik, Nodira, Uvaysiy, Anbar Otin singari mumtoz shoiralalar maslagiga mosligida ko'rinadi. Bular shoira asl orzulari ushaliyida, she'riyatda ayol obrazining teran mushohadakor fikrlar bilan chizilishida ko'rinadi. Ispan faylasufi Xose Ortega-i-Gasset shunday yozadi: "Har qaysi san'atning tarixi inson qalbining tomonlaridan birini ifodalashga bo'lgan qator urinishlardir. Xuddi shu narsa uni boshqa san'atlardan ajratib turadi. Bu urinishlar shunday bir egri chiziqni tashkil qiladiki, san'at

⁴ Румак Ю.С. Факторы формирования гендерных образов в культуре Японии: Автореф. дисс ... канд. культурологии. – Саратов: 2010.Б.23

kamalakning yengil o‘qi kabi shu chiziq bo‘ylab zamon qa‘riga o‘z maqsadi sari intiladi. Intihosiz ufqdagi shu nuqta har qaysi san‘atning yo‘nalishini, mohiyatini va ma‘nosini ko‘rsatib turadi”⁵. Haqiqatan ham, ijodkor fitratidan o‘sib chiqqan ulug‘ g‘oyalar optimistik kayfiyatga borib tutashadi. Barcha san‘at asarlarida bo‘lgani kabi sabab va oqibat falsafasi tuyg‘ular realizmini yuzaga chiqaradi. “Ayollar adabiyoti”da ayol qalbi tasviri, qalb suvrati aynan ikki mavjudlik jumbog‘ini tahlil qilishda yanada yorqinroq namoyon bo‘ladi.

Borliqni badiiy inkishof qilishda estetik munosabat muhim ahamiyat kasb etishi sinalgan hodisa. Ushbu nazariy aqida va tushuncha she‘riy shakl tadrijida ijodkor ideali bilan chambarchas bog‘liq tarzda yuzaga chiqadi. O.Gassetning ijodkor olamshumul voqelik bilan ommaga tanilishi aniq, ammo unda yuksak san‘at asari uchqunlari bo‘lmasa uzoq yashay olmaydi, degan ta‘rifi XX va XXI asrlar adabiyoti ko‘zgisida o‘zining haqiqat ekanligini isbotlab turibdi. Bugun ayol ijodkorlar olamidagi mana shu yashovchanlik davom etib, “Ayollar adabiyoti”ning shakllanishi va davomiyligini yuzaga chiqarib turibdi desak yanglishmagan bo‘lamiz.

Istiqloq davri adabiyotida Halima Axmedova, Farida Afro‘z, Zebo Mirzo, Xosiyat Rustamova, Xosiyat Bobomurodova kabi ijodkorlarning poetik olami, ularning badiiy ijodi adabiyotning shakllanishida, ma‘naviy xazinaning yuksalishida o‘z o‘rniga egadir. Shu bilan birga poetik mahorati yuksak bo‘lishiga qaramay asarlari yetarlicha o‘rganilmagan ijodkor ayollar talaygina. Maqsuda Ergasheva, Shahodat Isaxonova, Jamila Ergasheva kabilar shular jumlasidandir.

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⁵ Хосе Ортега-и-Гассет. Одам Ато жаннатда. Жаҳон адиблари адабиёт ҳақида. – Т.: «Маънавият», 2010.

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